

Managing Editor's Column

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This issue is again a typical J.UCS issue both as far as topics and geography are concerned, but it also shows a bit the direction J.UCS is moving: of the 13 authors, 6 are from Europe, 4 from China and 2 from North America. The distribution makes me ask our colleagues in Canada and USA to please also publish in J.UCS, and maybe even more important, to propose well-known computer scientist from USA and Canada for our editorial board. I'm sure you can find young, but already established researchers amongst your colleagues who might be interested and willing to give J.UCS some of their time once in a while and become a part of its success.

Actually, examining the distribution of contributions over the last years we also need more support from UK, France and Germany in our editorial board. Consider signing up and join one of the oldest electronic journals!

Also, I'm proud to inform you that the impact factor of J.UCS has increased considerably and is now 0.669, the 5-year impact factor being 0.788. In comparison, in 2009, the impact factor of the journal was 0.488, the 5-year impact factor 0.484. We thank the authors, guest editors and members of our editorial board for making this important increase possible.

Hope you find this issue interesting,

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

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